

Title

Are seed and information circulation networks related to the crop diversity and resilience of smallholder farms? A study protocol

Authors

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28 **Abstract**

29 Smallholder farming is predominant in regions that are particularly subject to climate change
30 worldwide, especially drylands, and particularly suffer from an increase in climatic shocks. In this
31 context, crop diversity is considered as an important asset for the resilience of smallholders who have
32 limited financial and material capitals, infrastructures and technologies. However, knowledge is limited
33 about the processes enhancing smallholders' access to crop diversity. Seed and associated information
34 circulation patterns are considered as a major driver of crop diversity availability and access, although
35 which circulation patterns enhance the availability of a large diversity pool at the collective level and
36 its access for farmers remains matter of debate.

37 The research protocol presented here, designed in the ARISER project (*Access to crop diversity and*
38 *small farms' resilience to climate variability in African drylands: The role of seed and information*
39 *networks*) funded by the European Research Council, is developed to address these critical gaps. This
40 protocol was designed for collecting comparable longitudinal and panel data across diverse contexts to
41 assess: (i) differences in farms' seed and associated information networks, and their socioeconomic
42 drivers; (ii) whether these differences in farm's networks relate to differences in their level of crop
43 diversity and temporal turnover, (iii) whether they relate to pluriannual indicators of farms' resilience
44 to shocks, mainly the temporal stability of crop production and households' ability to meet their food
45 and financial needs over time.

46 ARISER protocol is the first of this kind, covering four consecutive years and 2000 households in three
47 different although comparable study sites. We thus believe that sharing this protocol and the challenges
48 we met along its design, test and implementation can be of interest for the design of future research in
49 this domain and worth to be shared with our research community. This protocol is expected to improve
50 the general understanding of how seed and related information networks affect smallholders' ability to
51 use crop diversity in the face of disturbances, and to which extent this is mediated by socioeconomic
52 inequalities. Such understanding is needed to improve decision-making in the seed sector and better
53 address the specific challenges that smallholders face in adapting to global changes.

54 Keywords

55 Research protocol, crop diversity, seed circulation, resilience, smallholders

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61 **Introduction**

62 Smallholder farming is the dominant form of agriculture in a large part of the world, including Africa,
63 South-East Asia, Latin America, and tropical Islands (Samberg et al. 2016). Smallholder farmers
64 generally cultivate small areas and have limited access to infrastructure and to technologies including
65 mechanization, chemical inputs, and irrigation because of their low financial capital. Despite those
66 limited assets, they produce a substantial part of the world's food while having limited environmental
67 impacts as they mostly practice agroecological cultivation. Recent estimations indicate that farms of
68 less than five ha produce an estimated half of the world's food calories (Ricciardi et al. 2018). Small
69 farms thus can play a key role in sustaining food security while preserving natural resources and
70 biodiversity in the face of global challenges such as adaptation to climate change (Altieri and Nicholls
71 2017).

72 Smallholders largely rely on crop diversity for their livelihoods, as it is one of the main resources they
73 can mobilize to ensure production without substantial financial investment (Cervigni and Morris 2016).
74 A large part of smallholder lives in areas where the variability of the biophysical and socioeconomic
75 environment is high. For instance, smallholder agriculture is dominant in the drylands, where climatic
76 variability is high and is expected to increase dramatically in the future with major impacts on
77 agriculture (Knox et al. 2012, Porter et al. 2017, Cottrell et al. 2019). In these areas, cultivating a
78 diversity of crop species and varieties is frequently mentioned as a way to cope with the highly variable
79 environmental conditions as it strengthens households' capacity to meet their food and financial needs
80 in the face of perturbations (Altieri and Nicholls 2017, Vernooy 2022). Access to crop diversity and to
81 the information associated to the characteristics of the different crops is expected to be crucial for the
82 resilience of smallholders to environmental variability for two main reasons. First, the cultivation of
83 different crop species and varieties allows to buffer environmental variations of different kind,
84 especially climatic or economic ones (Renard and Tilman 2021, Loreau et al. 2021, Di Falco and Chavas
85 2008, Pascual, Jackson and Drucker 2013). Second, the capacity of farms to change crop species or
86 varieties is a key to adapting to changing conditions (Cooper et al. 2008, Magesa et al. 2023, Labeyrie
87 et al. 2021).

88 To be able to diversify or change their crops, farmers need access to adapted planting material, as seeds,
89 cuttings, or other propagules. To select adapted species and varieties, their own knowledge as well as
90 external information on crop characteristics are crucial. Such information encompasses for instance
91 crop varieties' growth-cycle length that condition their ability to withstand drought, or their current
92 price on local market. However, despite their obvious importance in smallholders' resilience to
93 environmental variability, the processes driving their access to crop diversity and information remain
94 largely ignored in agricultural policies and development programs (Coomes et al. 2015). Rather,
95 development programs in Africa and worldwide support the specialization and uniformization of crops

96 from the plot to the regional level, which increases the vulnerability of smallholder farming to climate
97 variability and has major implications for food security at the local, national and global levels (Khoury
98 et al. 2014, Renard and Tilman 2019). This uniformization is particularly sustained by the centralization
99 of seed and information circulation, which also limits opportunities to develop local agroecological
100 innovations and adaptations (Vanloqueren and Baret 2017, Coolsaet 2015).

101 Smallholders face the shared challenge of gaining greater recognition for the plurality of their seed
102 systems, and benefiting from governance of seed systems that is better suited to their needs (Coomes et
103 al. 2015, Westengen, Dalle and Mulesa 2023). Seed systems are defined as “combined activities of
104 actors, making use of plant materials and knowledge, that together are necessary for suppling seeds to
105 farmers” (Cromwell et al. 1993; Louwaars et Manicad 2022). Smallholder seed systems involve a range
106 of stakeholders and institutions of different kinds: farmers and local seed sellers on weekly markets and
107 peers (McGuire et Sperling 2016). Yet, in most countries where smallholder farming is predominant,
108 national public policies, legal frameworks, and development programs led by international agencies
109 tend to focus on centralizing seed production and distribution (Scoones and Thompson 2011, Louwaars,
110 de Boef and Edeme 2013). These initiatives aim, on one hand, to strengthen state programs for breeding
111 and disseminating new varieties, and on the other hand, to develop the private seed sector, both of which
112 primarily distribute certified seeds from improved varieties of a limited number of crop species (Mulesa
113 et al. 2021). This raises major concerns among scholars and farmers' organizations, who argue that these
114 actions do not adequately address the specific needs of smallholders in terms of crop seed diversity
115 (Coomes et al. 2015, Peschard and Randeria 2020). Calls especially multiply on the necessity to
116 consider the plurality of seed systems, and favor the emergence of new organization modalities between
117 actors, accounting for local organization modalities, for enhancing smallholder access to seed diversity
118 (Mulesa et al. 2021, Berthet et al. 2020). Determining which seed system organization is better suited
119 in this perspective is a key point of debate (Westengen, Dalle and Mulesa 2023, Louwaars and Manicad
120 2022).

121 The circulation of seed and associated information has especially been identified as potentially key for
122 the maintenance and dynamics of crop diversity in farms (Labeyrie et al. 2021b). Substantial research
123 has focused on analyzing seed circulation patterns in smallholder agriculture, and to a lesser extent
124 those of associated information. **Yet, a thoughtful understanding of how these patterns relate to**
125 **farms' crop diversity and related resilience outcomes is lacking.** Social network analysis
126 (Wasserman and Faust 1994) has been applied to analyze seed circulation in smallholder communities,
127 and to a lesser extent, the circulation of associated information (Box 1). However, the extent to which
128 different seed and information circulation patterns relate to farm-level outcomes—such as crop
129 diversity, temporal turnover, and the maintenance of key functions under perturbations—remains
130 poorly understood (Labeyrie et al. 2021b).

131 The research protocol presented in this article was designed to enhance our understanding of how seed
132 and information circulation patterns relate to crop diversity level and temporal turnover in small farms,
133 and to indicators of farms' resilience to perturbations. Additionally, it seeks to understand which
134 socioeconomic factors enhance or limit farmers capacity to access crop diversity through these
135 networks. Developed within the ARISER project (*Access to Crop Diversity and Small Farms'
136 Resilience to Climate Variability in African Drylands: The Role of Seed and Information Networks*)
137 funded by the European Research Council (Starting Grant 2022-2027), this protocol was designed for
138 collecting comparable longitudinal and panel data across diverse contexts to assess: (i) differences in
139 farms' seed and associated information networks, and their socioeconomic drivers; (ii) whether these
140 differences in farm's networks relate to differences in their level of crop diversity and temporal
141 turnover, (iii) whether they relate to pluriannual indicators of farms' resilience to shocks, mainly the
142 temporal stability of crop production and households' ability to meet their food and financial needs over
143 time.

144 This article aims at sharing this research protocol with the research community on seed systems, and
145 provide feedback on its implementation during the ARISER project. This unified and adaptable protocol
146 is expected to bring a methodological contribution to research on smallholder seed systems, helping to
147 draw general conclusions on the studied relationships. We expect that comparing results obtained
148 through a standardized method across three study sites, located in different regions but in similar
149 agroecosystems, will improve the general understanding of these linkages and that publishing this
150 protocol will stimulate the collection of comparable data across a range of contexts.

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Social network analysis (SNA) is a research field dedicated to studying social relationships, which has expanded in the social sciences since the 1950s (Borgatti et al., 2009). It encompasses a range of methods for analysing interaction matrices between pairs of social entities (e.g. individuals or organisations), which are represented as nodes. SNA focuses on network structure and is based on graph theory (Wasserman and Faust 1994). The methods cover network representation algorithms, node and network-level indicators, node clustering, and a range of specific statistical models. The objectives of social network analysis can be summarised as follows: first, to unravel the social processes involved in the formation of ties and network structure; and second, to explore the outcomes of network structure on systems' functioning and on individuals.

Since 2000, significant progress has been made in understanding the social processes that shape the circulation of seeds and associated information, thanks to the theory and methods of social network analysis (Coomes et al., 2015; Pautasso et al., 2013; Calvet-Mir and Salpeteur, 2016). The circulation of seeds and information in smallholder farming is a complex system involving multiple stakeholders, such as farmers, local seed sellers, government and non-government rural development organisations, and, less frequently, seed companies (McGuire & Sperling, 2016), as well as intricate interaction patterns between them. These networks differ in composition, i.e. the types of actors involved, as well as in structure. Some are organised around a small number of actors acting as hubs (e.g. Ricciardi, 2015), while others are distributed (Thomas et Caillon, 2016) or organised in clusters (e.g. Abizaid et al. 2018, Calvet-Mir et al., 2012). Literature also depicts the diverse properties of farmers' personal networks. Some farmers are more active than others in disseminating or receiving seeds (e.g. Thomas and Caillon, 2016), while others are connected to a wider range of actors (e.g. Isaac, 2012). A farmer's position within a community network can also differ; some farmers are situated at the periphery of the network, while others are at its core (Kawa et al., 2013, Calvet-Mir et al., 2012; Ricciardi, 2015). Lastly, this literature has provided valuable insights into the processes that shape the circulation of seeds and associated information. Notably, it has emphasised that individuals within the same social, cultural, or geographical group tend to exchange seeds more frequently (Labeyrie et al., 2016) and that the socio-economic characteristics of farm members influence their personal networks and their position within the broader community network (Wencelius et al., 2016). It also shows how the network structure can differ according to the crops within a given community (Porcuna-Ferrer et al., 2023).

Figure 1: illustration of different network structure and node's positions

167 **Hypotheses, research strategy and ethics**

168 **Conceptual framework**

169 The general objective of this protocol is to establish the first systematical assessment of the relationship
170 between seed and information circulation patterns, crop diversity and indicators of farm's resilience in
171 African dryland areas, subject to high climate variability. For this purpose, it combines concept and
172 methods from social and agricultural sciences, especially: (i) social network analysis, that studies
173 interactions between social actors (i.e. individuals or organizations) and how they are influenced by
174 actors' socioeconomic characteristics, as well as how they affect actors' access to resources (Borgatti
175 2009); (ii) agroecology, that studies linkages between crop diversity and the temporal stability of
176 production as well as farms' livelihood and outcomes (Bravo-Peña et Yoder 2024; Renard et Tilman
177 2021).

178 This protocol aims at testing three general hypotheses, (detailed hereafter): (1) Farms differ in their seed
179 and information sourcing networks because of socioeconomic disparities; (2) These differences in
180 networks relate to differences in farm's crop diversity and temporal turnover; (3) This is associated to
181 differences in farms' capacity to maintain key functions, such as crop production and households' needs
182 coverage, in the face of perturbations (i.e. resilience).

183 (1) Previous research in rural areas indicates that the properties of the social networks of some
184 categories of households limit their access to resources (Rockenbauch et Sakdapolrak 2017). The
185 categories especially include: (i) less wealthy households (e.g. Baird et Gray 2014), and households
186 whose heads belong to the following categories: (ii) ethnic minorities or migrants (e.g. Hoang et al.
187 2018), (iii) women (e.g. Torkelsson 2007), (iv) young people (e.g. Cassidy et Barnes 2012). Thus, the
188 protocol aims at testing whether **farm and farmers characteristics in terms of economic status,**
189 **identity and date of settlement, gender and age are related to differences in seed and information**
190 **network indicators, such as the number and diversity of connections, and position in the**
191 **community network (e.g. center vs periphery).**

192 (2) Social network research has largely theorized and tested how the structure and composition of
193 communities' social networks affect the richness and diversity of resources available for their members
194 (e.g. Putnam 1995), and how an individual's personal social network and position in the whole network
195 influences access to resources (e.g. Lin et al. 2001; Burt 2002) (Figure 1). Yet, both collective and
196 individual levels were rarely treated together in Social Network Analysis (Agneessens et Koskinen
197 2016). Following the multilevel social network framework proposed by these authors, we hypothesize
198 that the network patterns at both community (e.g., village) and farms' levels affect farm crop diversity
199 and its temporal dynamics as: (i) the pool of crop diversity available at the collective level and its
200 dynamics depend on the community seed network patterns, and (ii) the access of farms to this pool

201 depends on their position in the community network and on patterns of their own network. Based on
 202 this literature, the protocol aims at testing whether **the crop diversity level and the crop turnover in**
 203 **farms over time are related to seed and information network characteristics at the community**
 204 **and farm levels**. At the community level, indicators encompass the density of connections in the
 205 community network, the diversity of connections, and global structural patterns (e.g. distributed, core-
 206 periphery, or cluster structure.). At the farm level, indicators cover the degree (number of connections),
 207 connections diversity, and centrality in the whole network.

208 (3) According to the “*insurance hypothesis*” for which increasing evidence emerge from agroecology
 209 literature, maintaining a higher level of crop diversity over time is expected to insure more stable crop
 210 production over time, especially in contexts where inter-annual climate variability is high (Renard et
 211 Tilman 2021). More broadly, studies in different contexts report the contribution of crop diversity to
 212 the maintenance of food availability and income in the face of shocks, although results appear strongly
 213 context dependent (Bravo-Peña et Yoder 2024). We thus expect that farms having an enhanced access
 214 to crop diversity would be more resilient to shocks in smallholder farming contexts where climate
 215 variability is high. The protocol thus aims at testing whether **farms presenting seed and information**
 216 **networks patterns associated to a higher crop diversity and turnover also present a higher and**
 217 **more stable crop production over time, as well as household’s needs coverage.**

218 *Figure 1. Main network patterns at the community and farm level expected to affect crop diversity level*
 219 *and crop turnover in farms. The nodes represent the social units (e.g., the farms), and the ties represent*
 220 *their interactions (e.g., seed diffusion).*

Community-level network patterns and effect	Illustration	Farm-level network patterns and effect	Illustration
Network connectivity: density of connections. <i>Enhances resources diffusion, but may reduce their diversity.</i>		Degree: number of direct connections the farm (<i>in red</i>) has. <i>Increases access to diversified resources.</i>	Low High
Network diversity: heterogeneity of actors (<i>in colors</i>) in a network and of connections between different actors. <i>Increases resource diversity.</i>		Network diversity: heterogeneity of the farm's connections. <i>Increases access to diversified resources.</i>	Low High
Core-periphery structure: extent to which a network is organized around a small number of actors having a large number of connections, acting as hubs (<i>in red</i>). <i>Enhances resources diffusion, but may reduce their diversity.</i>		Tie redundancy: extent to which the actors with whom the farm is connected are themselves interconnected. <i>Limits access to diversified resources.</i>	Low High
Cluster structure: extent to which a network is composed of subgroups (<i>in colors</i>) where connections between actors are denser within than between groups. <i>Limits diffusion between groups, but maintains or increases the diversity of resources at the collective level.</i>		Centrality: extent to which the farm is at the core of a network: <i>Increases access to diversified resources.</i>	Low High

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222 Research strategy

223 To test these hypotheses, longitudinal and panel farm surveys were designed in ARISER project to
 224 collect comparable field data in three dryland areas in North Morocco, central Senegal and South-

225 Western Madagascar (Box 2), where farmers are mostly smallholders who practice rainfed cultivation
226 of cereals and legumes and face an increasing inter-annual rainfall variability. Covering study sites in
227 different although comparable context allows bringing more general results that go beyond those of
228 case studies. This protocol is dedicated to smallholder seed systems that share common characteristics
229 and challenges. Although it was applied to smallholder agricultural systems located in drylands in the
230 frame of ARISER project, it was thought to be applicable to other climatic and agronomic contexts as
231 far as smallholder farming is concerned.

232 These study areas were selected because they are representative of biodiversity-based small-scale
233 farming that is practiced by the large majority of farmers throughout African drylands, having limited
234 access to agricultural technologies and infrastructures (Lowder et al. 2016; Ricciardi et al. 2018). They
235 were also selected because they are located in areas prone to recurrent rainfall deficit, which allows
236 investigating the linkages between seed and information network patterns, crop diversity and its
237 outcomes (i.e. the stability production, household needs coverage). Farmers in the three study sites
238 combine the production of food crops for self-consumption and local sale, and the production of cash
239 crops for sale on urban markets or for export. The seed systems from which they source their seeds
240 combine a diversity of actors: farmers, governmental and non-governmental rural development
241 organizations, and private actors. Although such a coexistence of actors was found in the three study
242 sites, the share of seeds obtained by farmers from each actor type differ between sites. The three
243 countries where the study takes place also present similar challenges regarding smallholder seed system
244 governance. Public policies and international development agencies support the centralized seed sector
245 that involves state and private actors for the dissemination of certified seeds from a few species and
246 varieties. Generally speaking, these actions poorly match the specific needs of smallholders, mainly
247 because species and varieties distributed are few and rarely adapted to the diversity of local growing
248 conditions and uses, and because seeds are costly (Almekinders and Louwaars 2002).

249 In each country, study sites include ten communities located in the same commune (i.e. smallest
250 administrative unit). This allows testing for the effect of different community network patterns within
251 a same social-ecological context. Longitudinal data collection is being conducted over four consecutive
252 years (2023-2026) to capture inter-annual variations and test the hypothesis concerning the temporal
253 dynamics of crop diversity and the stability of crop production and household's needs fulfillment.
254 Surveys are conducted after the last harvest of the agricultural year, during periods where farmers are
255 available.

256 Within ARISER project, the data collected through the farm survey protocol described in this article,
257 mainly dedicated to quantitative analysis, are combined with: (i) surveys among seed sellers on local
258 markets, (ii) qualitative data collected through a variety of approaches such as ethnographic surveys,
259 participant observations, serious games and participatory workshops, (iii) extensive literature review,
260 including "grey literature" and policy documents. Data collected through these various approaches

261 cover topics related to national seed politics and laws, seed sector governance, development programs
 262 targeting the seed sector in the studied region, seed markets, as well as the local norms and rules
 263 regulating seed circulation in rural communities, and crop diversity management. Although the project
 264 is based on a mixed-method approach, combining quantitative and qualitative methods, these latter
 265 methods are not described in this article.

266 *Box 2: a. Map of the study sites according to dryland geographical distribution in Africa (data sourced*
 267 *online from UNEP-WCMC 2007), b. Study sites description, c. Seed systems context in each country.*

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b. Study sites description

Site	Climate (UNEP-WCMC 2007)	Landscape	Main crop	Population	Dynamics
Morocco, Tangier-Tetouan-Al Hoceima region (Bni Garfet commune)	Semi-arid to dry sub-humid, Mediterranean	Fields both located in the plains (profound soils) and on the hills' slopes.	Wheat, barley, chickpea, fava bean Olive trees	Jbala (Arabic- speaking)	Rural exodus, aging farming population.
Senegal, Kaffrine region (Boulel commune)	Semi-arid, Sahelian	Flat plains with a dominant sandy soils and temporarily hydromorphic clayish soils.	Millet, cowpea, groundnut,	Wolof, Sereer and Halpulaar	Rural exodus, aging farming population.
Madagascar, Atsimo-Andrefana region (Soahazo commune)	Semi-arid	Alluvial plain, both flood recession (alluvial soils) and rainfed fields (red sands).	Corn, Cassava, Sweet potatoe, cowpea Cotton	Massikoro, Antandroy	Seasonal migrations, both from and to the study area.

c. Seed systems description

(1) **The occidental pre-Rif region in North Morocco.** The country integrated the UPOV system meaning that national laws strictly regulate seed production and sale. A state company (SONACOS) has a substantial monopoly for certified seed distribution, that is done all over the country through local distribution points and is associated to credit opportunities. SONACOS mainly distribute varieties that were anciently released by international research centers, which poorly match farmers needs according to some authors (Alary, Yigezu, Bassi 2020). Since 1975, when SONACOS was created to take charge of the production and distribution of selected seeds, successive national agricultural development programs have encouraged farmers to buy seeds from this company (Khrouz 1992). Today, the new agricultural development plans (Plan Maroc Vert, Plan Génération Green) follow this way. Apart from that, studies in different parts of Morocco indicate that local markets (*souk*) are important sources of seeds for farmers, as well as peer-to-peer seed circulation in some areas (Chentoufi et al. 2014).

(2) **The Groundnut Basin in the west-center of Senegal.** Although the country did not join the UPOV system yet, this objective is pursued and national seed laws are closely in line with its principles (Bloukounon et al. 2024). Breeding and certified seed distribution involves both state and private actors, the latter ones being more involved on rice and vegetables. The multiplication and distribution of certified seeds is done by three types of actors: seed companies, individual seed producers and cooperatives. Farmers' access to certified seeds is incentivized through subsidies, mainly for groundnut seeds, but these are largely insufficient regarding farmers' needs. Studies in different part of the Senegal, including the groundnut basin indicate that certified seeds are rarely bought by smallholder farmers in our study area, and that farmers dominantly source seeds in local markets (*louma*) and through peer-to-peer networks (Porcuna-Ferrer et al. 2024, Cobelli et al. 2023).

(3) **South-western Madagascar Atsimo-Andrefana region.** Madagascar did not join UPOV system so far, but laws follow the OCDE scheme that is closely related. Quality declared seeds scheme, which covers local varieties, exist in the South of Madagascar (Cabot et Hoerner 2024) but do not cover our study area although it may be extended in the future. Breeding is mainly done by the national institute FOFIFA and its research partners (e.g. CIMMYT CIRAD, AfricaRice, IRRI, JICA; Beauval and Di Leonardo 2016). Seed production and distribution is done by different structures, including NGOs, farmers' organizations, and private societies part of which also import seeds (e.g. hybrid maize seeds). Actions targeting the seed sector in Madagascar mainly relies on international programs (Razafimbelonaina and Bélières 2023). In practice, other studies indicated that smallholder farmers rarely buy certified seeds, and mainly use farm seeds either self-produced, obtained on the local market, or from peers (Cabot et Hoerner 2024).

269

270 **Funding**

271 This protocol was developed, tested and implemented in the frame of the ARISER project (*Access to*
272 *Crop Diversity and Small Farms' Resilience to Climate Variability in African Drylands: The Role of*
273 *Seed and Information Networks*) led by Vanesse Labeyrie who received funding from the European
274 Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No101041069.

275 **Ethics**

276 Ethics is of major importance in this type of research and specific efforts were made to cover the
277 different ethics issues in ARISER project, which we believe deserves to be shared for guiding future
278 research. The research protocol presented has been reviewed and validated by different external ethics
279 boards, and benefits from external advice to improve the ethical approach. The Description of Action

280 of the project has been first reviewed by the European Union Research Council ethics panel (European
281 Commission 2022.01.31). Then, the Consultative Ethics Committee for Partnership Research (CCERP)
282 of French Institute for Research and Development (IRD) validated our approach and provided
283 recommendations to further include some ethical issues (CCERP – 2022.05.04). The project benefits
284 from an Ethical Advisor to provide guidance and advice on ethical subjects linked to project's
285 implementation. The project governance bodies include a "Steering, monitoring and ethics committee"
286 consisting of partners and members of the project and external experts.

287 The project team also developed an internal code of ethics, written in a collaborative way by the
288 different project members. This code of ethics explains a set of measures that project members, partners
289 and providers, are expected to follow to comply with regulatory obligations and project values, and to
290 avoid any harm and maximize the benefits to the communities and to project members. This code of
291 ethics covers both internal and external aspects. Internal ethics concern the relationships among
292 members of the project's team, such as relationship between advisors and students and between the
293 different partners, and it included gender issues. A particular attention is paid to build balanced and fair
294 partnership with research institutions in the different countries where the protocol is applied, involving
295 partners at each stage of the research, from the project design to the publication. External ethics rather
296 covered issues related to relationships with the communities in which the study takes place, and
297 especially people who participate in the surveys. It covered especially issues related to consent,
298 information privacy, people respect, and benefit sharing.

299 The protocol complies with the different regulatory frameworks related to the nature of the data
300 collected, namely the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the national research permits, and
301 the Nagoya protocol. In consultation with the Data Protection Officer of the host institution, the team
302 put in place several measures to comply with the GDPR. A Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA)
303 was conducted by the Cirad's external data protection officer (DPO) since the study leads to
304 interviewing vulnerable people, including on subjects leading to the collection of sensitive data within
305 the meaning of the GDPR (ethnic origin), on areas that could lead to qualifying large-scale data
306 collection.

307 Free Prior Informed Consent (FPIC) forms are used to cover the issues related to both participants' data
308 privacy and to intellectual property, including aspects related to Nagoya protocol. The FPIC is adapted
309 to each field site and translated in the local language of the study site. The main sections of the form
310 include: (i) a brief description of the project objectives and team, the data controller, and the purposes
311 of personal data processing, (ii) what information will be collected from participants during the survey,
312 (iii) how the data will be stored and who will get access to it, (iv) how the data will be treated and
313 disseminated in the project, which includes the description of the procedure for the secret information
314 (specifying that any publication or dissemination material will only cover aggregated data at a level that
315 makes individual re-identification impossible), (v) what is the procedure for third parties to access the

316 data in future projects, (vi) conditions and contacts for withdrawing from the survey and exercising
317 GDPR rights, and (vii) indications on Nagoya Protocol compliance. Consent is first sought from local
318 authorities and communities' representatives. During data collection, consent from each interviewee is
319 collected, who should have reached their legal majority. In case of impossibility to obtain written
320 consent from the interviewee, we collected verbal consent with a witness that certify it was obtained
321 under appropriate conditions. The witnesses sign a document to attest the consent of the interviewee
322 (section A of the survey questionnaires provided in S1). Awareness is raised on personal data protection
323 with each project member, interviewers and providers through adequate training.

324 Approval from the pertinent national authorities was thought in each country and region through the
325 collaborations with local research institutions. The presented research complies with the national rules
326 concerning field research in each country, and research permits were granted with the support of our
327 local collaborators when required. In Madagascar, such permits were sought from the Ministère de
328 l'Environnement et du Développement Durable with the support of our local partners (Université
329 d'Antananarivo). In Morocco, it was sought by our research collaborators (Faculté Polydisciplinaire de
330 Larache) from the Ministère de l'Intérieur, and the governor of Larache province. In Senegal, no
331 research permit is required due to the formal contractual collaboration between CIRAD (Centre de
332 coopération internationale de recherche en agronomie et développement) and ISRA (National
333 Senegalese Institute for Agricultural Research).

334 Specific attention is payed to access and benefit sharing arising from the use of genetic resources and
335 traditional knowledge in research and development, which are key principles of the Nagoya protocol.
336 Since traditional knowledge is at play (during the farmer survey, we collect data on the varieties used
337 by farmers, their origins, usages, agronomic and organoleptic features), researcher investigators follow
338 the national procedures specified by the focal points of Nagoya protocol in countries that are part of it,
339 and reach agreement of authorities prior to data collection.

340 Last, particular attention is payed to benefit sharing with the survey's participants (e.g. farmers or other
341 actors), extending beyond the villages surveyed. Participatory workshops are organized with farmers
342 and with the rural development organizations involved in the dissemination of seed and associated
343 information at the local scale in each study site to present and discuss the results of the project. A
344 participatory approach is used, by presenting the results of the project using interactive tools and to
345 stimulate feedback from participants and debate. This makes it possible to discuss the impacts of
346 different modes of dissemination of crops and associated information on farmers' access to this
347 resource, and how it affects farmers differently depending on their socioeconomic characteristics. It
348 also aims at stimulating debate on the consequences of these different modes of organization to enable
349 farmers to adapt to climate variability. One workshop is also organized in each country with national
350 decision-makers and international development agencies to present the results of both data analysis and
351 local workshops. The workshops aim to raise decision- makers' awareness of the need to incorporate

352 the wide range of seed systems and management practices in development plans. We expect the
353 workshops to provide concrete elements for the development of innovative seed systems, by revealing
354 which configurations of interactions between the different actors enable the best access to crop diversity
355 for smallholder farmers (Louafi et al. 2021). Benefit sharing actions are also developed for the research
356 partners in each country where the project takes place, by designing dedicated training and capacity-
357 building actions for the local students that participate in the project.

358 **Surveys setting**

359 The preparation stage of our protocol consists in selecting the study communities in each study site,
360 adapting the survey grid to each context, and selecting and training the team for data collection. We
361 present bellow how this preparation stage was conducted in ARISER project, as an example of how this
362 can be implemented, although the procedure should be adapted to each project and context. This
363 preparation consisted of two steps of field visits conducted the first year of the project (2022-2023) in
364 each study site, involving the core-team members and local collaborators. During these visits, we
365 conducted individual and focus-group discussions with customary authorities, leaders (e.g. cooperatives
366 presidents), notables, lineage chiefs and farmers.

367 The objectives of the first field-visit were: (i) to introduce the study (e.g. team members, planned
368 activities and their schedule) to the various local administrative and customary authorities, (ii) to request
369 the consent of the administrative authorities to carry out the study in the area, and (iii) to collect specific
370 information and recommendations that could help selecting the social units for the survey. This covered
371 especially information on the demographic, economic and ethno-linguistic characteristics of the
372 population, dominant cash and subsistence crops, farming practices, main sources of seeds, local
373 markets, names of organizations and projects related to seed and crop management. It also allowed to
374 identify the main seed distributors in the area, in particular: (i) seed sellers on local weekly markets, (ii)
375 cooperatives, and (iii) private or state actors distributing seeds in the area. The information collected
376 allowed us to select the study units in each of the sites, i.e. social units in which relations between
377 people, and especially exchanges of seeds and information, are expected to be more frequent than with
378 outsiders.

379 Our objective was to select 8 to 12 communities in each study site, with a relatively homogeneous
380 population size of 50 to 200 households per social unit. We limited the population size because applying
381 social network surveys and analysis to large social units raises particular challenges. The selection of
382 the study units was done both based on the interest of local authorities' in taking part in the study, and
383 based on the following criteria: (i) similar in terms of agroecological and climatic conditions, (ii)
384 representative of the different ethno-linguistic groups living in the area, (iii) relying on at least one
385 common weekly market for seed sourcing, (iv) represent the diversity of the actors of the seed sector in
386 the area (e.g. organizations and projects), so as to include units within which farmers have different

387 opportunities for accessing seeds. The social units selected may or may not overlap with administrative
388 divisions: in Morocco they correspond to *douars* (villages), in Senegal to *deukk ba* (villages), and in
389 Madagascar they correspond either to an entire *fokontany* (large village), or to a hamlet belonging to a
390 fokontany (small village within the administrative limits of a fokontany). Prior to conducting the
391 surveys, we validated the list of the selected social units with the administrative and customary
392 authorities and seek their consent to carry out the surveys in their locality.

393 The objective of the second field-visit was to collect information for adapting the generic survey grid
394 and test it in each site context. The generic survey grid was initially built to define the nature of the
395 questions and the scales at which they were to be asked (i.e. individual, household, farm, field, species,
396 named variety). It was tested in each field site and adapted so as to keep the data comparable across
397 sites. To this end, we conducted between 20 and 30 semi-structured interviews with farmers and key
398 stakeholders that were particularly knowledgeable about agricultural systems. This preliminary survey
399 was conducted in a village of the study site that was not selected in our final sample. Adapting the
400 generic survey grid to the study site meant, on the one hand, asking the same questions to as many
401 people as possible in order to obtain the most exhaustive list of answers possible reflecting reality (for
402 instance, to set the list of crop species or varieties); on the other hand, testing different question
403 formulations and several survey form structures in order to build one that was as adapted as possible to
404 social and cultural norms and customs, and to farmers' ways of thinking. The way questions were
405 formulated in each context were extensively discussed with our research partners in each country and
406 with the data collection teams, and we also integrated the feedback of participants to the preliminary
407 surveys. This work led to a first version of the survey form for each site, that was implemented on the
408 KoboCollect application and that was used to train the local team who conducted the survey. A
409 particular challenge was to keep the duration of interviews acceptable while the topic of the surveys
410 required a detailed understanding of both socioeconomic and agronomic aspects of farms.

411 The selection of the teams who conducted the surveys was done in collaboration with our research
412 partners in each country. The interviewers were either professional ones used to work for our partner
413 research centers, or students from the study area or with a good knowledge of it and proven experience
414 in this type of survey work. The selection of the data collection team and its training was key to limit
415 the data comparability issue that can result from the fact that different individuals collected the data.
416 The training was done by the same researcher (J. Mariel) in the three study sites to limit differences in
417 data collection and ensure that surveys are conducted in comparable ways. The training covered one
418 day of presentation of the questionnaire and exchanges with the participants, and three days of tests in
419 the field. Feedback from the team during the test days was progressively integrated into the form in
420 order to build an improved version of the questionnaire to be applied in the social units selected for our
421 study. Particular attention to the way in which each question was understood by interviewers was paid
422 during their training, in order to ensure that the questions were properly formulated and understood.

423 During the training, collectively defining the most correct wording and translation possible for each
424 question with interviewers was instrumental. This was required to avoid as much as possible
425 misunderstanding and differences in surveys implementation between interviewers, as each individual
426 conducts the surveys based on his/her own past experiences and with his/her own posture and approach.
427 The training provided to local interviewers was therefore built up in a participative and collaborative
428 way, in order to involve the interviewers as much as possible in the study and enable them to share their
429 knowledge and skills. Despite this common training for all interviewers in ARISER study, we
430 acknowledge that interviewers may have misunderstood the objective of some questions and may also
431 pay less effort than trained researchers in getting the accurate answer from farmers. Assessment of
432 interviewer's bias is thus being implemented prior to the data analysis.

433 Once this first stage of survey preparation had been completed, farm surveys started in 2023 and are
434 repeated each year with the same households for four years, so the farm household data collection
435 protocol ends in 2027. A particular challenge in this longitudinal survey was to limit participants
436 saturation and disengagement as we asked repeatedly similar questions for four consecutive years. We
437 paid particular attention to train the interviewers team to explain the reason for that, and this was
438 detailed in the letter of information for the Prior Informed Consent Procedure. Organizing workshops
439 to present and debate results with survey participants was also key to maintain their involvement, and
440 raising discussions about their own interest in relation with the topic of the project.

441 **Farms and participants recruitment strategy**

442 First, an exhaustive sampling of farms involved in seed and information circulation in each community
443 was seek, in the objective to conduct complete network analysis at the community level (Wasserman
444 and Faust 1994). Complete network allows to analyze the patterns of seed circulation between
445 community members and the position of farms in this network. However, we encounter some issues to
446 meet this objective for different reasons. Firstly, it was not possible to make sure that all the farms were
447 surveyed and to estimate the participation rate because getting access to preexisting census of farms
448 was not possible, and local authorities were reluctant that researchers conduct their own census. This
449 problem was faced in all the field sites of ARISER project. Secondly, it is frequent that interviews could
450 not be done in some farms because the heads are not present due to seasonal migration, or because they
451 refuse to participate in the survey.

452 Second, we decided in each site who should be interviewed in each farm based on literature review,
453 observations done during preliminary surveys, and discussions with the local collaborators. Crop
454 management practices at the farm level are the result of complex decision-making processes and actions
455 involving different household members. Studies generally interview farm heads, considered as having
456 a good knowledge of the different facets of crop management at the farm level, but some studies indicate
457 that this strategy does provide an accurate picture of the whole seed portfolio and sourcing channels at

458 the farm level (Wencélius et al. 2016). We initially aimed at interviewing both the male and female
459 farm heads, as both can grow different crops. In the case of polygamous households, it was agreed that
460 the first spouse generally gets a good knowledge of what the others were doing, although we agree this
461 approach presents some limits. However, we were constrained to review this objective for different
462 reasons. First, in most cases it was difficult to find both the man and the women available for the
463 interview within households. This was especially the case in Madagascar, where we decided to
464 interview one or the other depending on their availability, as both get a good general knowledge of what
465 is cultivated in the farm. In Senegal, men frequently migrate to find a job during the dry season where
466 the interviews were conducted, which raises problems to interview them. In many cases, women were
467 also very busy at the time of the interview for food preparation and house work, and it was not easy to
468 convince them to participate. We encounter difficulties conducting interviews with women because of
469 cultural habits, particularly in Senegal and Morocco. In some cases, men do not let the interviewers
470 conduct surveys with their wives because they argue that they knew all that was done in the farm. Men
471 could even feel offended that we asked to interview women on this topic. This potentially impacted our
472 ability to document the seed management of some crops (e.g. those cultivated in home gardens), where
473 women appear to play an important role.

474 **Farms' surveys content**

475 The farm surveys (see the survey questionnaire in S1) are conducted on a yearly base and take place
476 after the main harvest period. In ARISER project, they cover the target crops (cereals, legumes, and
477 tubers) cultivated during the year preceding the survey (starting from the first sowing period). For
478 instance, the surveys conducted in 2023 covered: the period between November 2022 and August 2023
479 in Madagascar, between May 2022 and December 2022 in Senegal, and between October 2021 and
480 September 2022 in Morocco.

481 The farm surveys are based on questionnaires structured in two main sections (sections D and C of
482 Figure 2) that aim at collecting general data concerning the characteristics of the households, farms and
483 fields that are relevant to understand crop and seed management, and level of crop production. Indeed,
484 this protocol apprehends crop diversity (species and varieties) management as embedded in the general
485 household functioning and adopts a systemic perspective for its analysis. This implies accounting for
486 the effects of the different management scales (i.e. household, farm, field) within farms and the different
487 aspects of farms' functioning and of farmers' decision-making concerning crops and seeds. In this
488 perspective, the questionnaires are designed to collect data covering the different management scales.
489 In ARISER project, we decided to collect detailed data on households' socioeconomic characteristics
490 and field management only the first year of the survey to characterize the farming system, but this was
491 not repeated the following years to limit the time spent during the survey.

492

493 *Figure 2: Organization of the questionnaire for farm surveys with the different organizational levels at which*
 494 *data were collected and the types of data collected (for more details, see the survey questionnaire in S1).*

495

496 (i) **Farm’s characteristics:** At the household scale (section D, Figure 2 and S1), the
 497 questionnaire covers the socioeconomic characteristics, including household composition,
 498 economic and livelihood activities, and indicators of wealth. Characteristics of the
 499 individuals chiefly involved in crop management (household heads) are also documented,
 500 including education level, age, gender, geographical origin and mother tongue. It also
 501 includes some questions on households’ capacity to meet their needs for food and income,
 502 and the problems they faced for crop production, as well as their appreciation concerning
 503 access to seed and information. At the field scale (section C.1), the questionnaire covers
 504 characteristics that are important for crop diversity management, such as modalities of
 505 access to land, agricultural tools and farm assets, data on the agroecological conditions (soil
 506 type and topography) and on farming practices (e.g. use of inputs, type of soil preparation,
 507 type of crops’ association).
 508 This section of the questionnaire is designed to overcome several issues that were
 509 encountered during the test stage, and we ended in defining indicators and formulating
 510 questions that limit these issues. Collecting accurate data on sensitive aspects such as the
 511 economic status and assets of the households, the land area, and the agricultural production,
 512 is especially challenging. In some contexts, respondents are reluctant to provide this type
 513 of information either because of local norms and taboos, or because they fear that such
 514 information could be used by the authorities to control them, and to regulate their access to
 515 state support systems and subsidies. In some cases, respondents don’t know the surface

516 they cultivate, which is a classical problem faced in this type of survey, and estimating
517 these surfaces based on the time spent preparing the soil or sowing can be very challenging.

518

519 (ii) **Seed baskets:** After these general sections, the questionnaire goes into sections dedicated
520 to the seed basket and associated information, that covers all the seed lots cultivated by the
521 household over the last year for cereal, legume and tuber crops. A seed lot is the set of
522 seeds of a given farmer's named variety he/she reported obtaining from the same source on
523 the same date. For documenting seed baskets while limiting memory issues, respondents
524 were first asked to list the species of legumes, cereals or tuber crops they have grown over
525 the past year (section C.2). A predefined list of species for these crops was used to
526 systematically check for the presence or absence of each in the farm. Then (section C.2.a),
527 for each crop species, farmers were asked to list all the varieties that have been grown in
528 the farm over the last year based on the name they use to identify them (hereafter referred
529 to as "named varieties"). The varieties named by farmers can cover different types of
530 biological entities, they can be landraces, i.e. a set of individual plants presenting similar
531 morphological characteristics according to farmers and hence identified using the same
532 name by them but that can cover a substantial morphological and genetic diversity (Louette
533 2000, Villa et al. 2006), but also sometimes DHS registered varieties (Distinct,
534 Homogeneous and Stable), or crop populations that result from a mix between landraces
535 and DHS varieties (referred as 'creolized varieties' in the literature). A predefined list of
536 varieties names is suggested to farmers based on preliminary surveys, but the option to add
537 new names is possible. Characteristics of the varieties are recorded, with a focus on their
538 origin according to the farmer, i.e. whether they are: (i) local farmers' varieties, considered
539 by the interviewees to have been grown in the area before they started farming, (ii)
540 introduced varieties that appear in the area after they started farming, in which case we
541 documented when possible if farmers think they were distributed through official channels
542 such as private seed companies or development organizations, or if they are varieties
543 introduced from other regions, and (iii) varieties whose origin is unknown. We also
544 estimated the age of the variety in the study area by asking respondents whether their
545 parents were already growing this variety. We document the quantity sowed and harvested
546 for each variety, the use or destination of the harvest products (e.g. household food self-
547 consumption, animal food, grain or seed sale), the farmer's level of satisfaction with the
548 harvest and any problems encountered that affected production levels. We also asked
549 farmers about the reasons for cultivating this particular variety.

550 For each named variety (section C.2), we ask farmers to list and describe the different seed
551 lots (i.e. all the seed of the same variety obtained from the same source on the same date
552 by the household) they sow over the past year, and to describe each seed lot source and the

553 social tie involved (sections C.2.a and C.2.c). The seed lots were differentiated depending
554 on whether respondents reported they had been self-produced on-farm or obtained from
555 outside, in case it was self-produced, we asked when the seed lot was sourced outside the
556 farm for the last time (Figure 3).

557 Then, we record the external sources where the seeds were last obtained based on a
558 categorization from preliminary surveys that defined five main categories of source.
559 Certain categories have been added and adapted depending on the study site, based on the
560 surveys conducted among seed distributors. To cover the various less frequently cited
561 sources, we leave the possibility to farmer to cite other seed sources (category “other
562 source”). Additional information is then collected concerning the seed source, including its
563 geographical location, its gender and its name in case it is an individual located in the
564 research area, and its location and name in case it is an organization or a project. In case
565 the seed transaction involves two individuals, the social tie between the seed receiver and
566 provider is described as follows: (i) no pre-existing tie, (ii) acquaintance (i.e. they know
567 each other but don’t have a close social relationship), (iii) friendship, (iv) neighboring (of
568 house or fields), (v) familial tie (kinship). In case of a kinship tie, we use a standardized
569 way of coding precisely the relationship to be able to identify its precise nature. Last,
570 information is collected concerning the reasons for seeking seeds from this specific seed
571 source, with predefined options suggested (see questionnaire in S1) and the possibility to
572 add new ones. We also collect information on the nature of the transaction, i.e. if it is
573 monetized, in the form of gifts or exchanges, or inherited.

574 The section C.2.b aims at documenting the sources through which farmers get information
575 concerning each crop varieties and that motivated them to start their cultivation. In this
576 perspective, farmers are invited to describe how they got the idea to grow this particular
577 named variety. First, we record if this is based on farmers’ own experience, or on external
578 advice or observations. If it is external, we document the characteristics of the information
579 source and social tie involved, that are described in the same way as for the seed
580 transactions.

581 For both seed and information sourcing, the name generator approach is applied by asking
582 the interviewees to cite freely the name of seed/information providers and we collect other
583 information to make possible their identification a-posteriori (age, gender, precise
584 location). The a-posteriori identification of these individuals is made in collaboration with
585 the responsible of the surveys in each country, when necessary. Applying a roster approach
586 is usually recommended for collecting such data in a systematic way (Wasserman and Faust
587 1994), based on a predefined list of households. This was not possible in the different study
588 sites covered by ARISER projects as no census existed or local authorities were not allowed
589 to transmit them, and they were also reluctant to allow the research team to conduct a

590 census. The name-generator approach can lead to errors in identifying a-posteriori the
 591 individuals from whom the farmers obtained seeds and information. This is especially
 592 challenging when homonymy is frequent, which requires collecting precise information on
 593 the location, age and spouse of the provider. Furthermore, collecting data on the precise
 594 identity of seed or information providers is very sensitive, and interviewees can be reluctant
 595 to provide this information. Accurately collecting this type of data requires trust, which is
 596 difficult to attain in such large-scale surveys where the interviewers stay a limited time in
 597 the communities. Farmers' memory is also one limit, as some events of seed or information
 598 can be easily forgotten.

599

600 *Figure 3: Detail of the different data collected through the questionnaire sections on seed and information*
 601 *sourcing.*

602

603 **Questionnaire design and digital implementation**

604 In ARISER study, KoboToolbox software and the KoboCollect application were used to facilitate large-
 605 scale surveys and reduce the risk of interviewers' errors, by eliminating paper-based data collection and
 606 individual data entry into Excel spreadsheets. The software offers the possibility to build a survey form
 607 with different response modalities (e.g. integer or decimal, single choice, multiple choice, free text),
 608 and whose structure can include question nesting, repetition and loops. The survey form can be built
 609 offline using the xlsx language. This allows the variable names and modalities to be defined at the same

610 time as the questions are formulated and the possible answers are listed. Thus, each question
611 corresponds to a variable, and each possible answer corresponds to a modality. So, when a survey is
612 carried out, i.e. a form is filled in, it is sent to the software server and the data collected is directly
613 recorded and stored in an Excel spreadsheet according to the pre-defined variable and modality names.
614 For field surveys, the KoboCollect application enables the form to be downloaded onto a tablet.

615 **Data management and analysis**

616 **Data management**

617 ARISER Data Management Plan describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected,
618 processed and stored project. As the project processes personal data, measures have been implemented
619 to ensure adequate protection : (i) raise awareness among users (both internal and external to the project)
620 working with personal data to the risks associated with privacy issues, (ii) establish procedures for
621 processing, sharing and storage personal data in line with the General Data Protection Regulation, (iii)
622 use secure Information Technologies solutions with user access limited to the data they need and use
623 encrypted electronic devices (hardware, computer, phones), (iv) Include special clauses applying to
624 personal data in providers' contracts. Personal data allowing individuals identification are only accessed
625 by the team members, who are contractually committed to comply with the privacy rules.

626 Once submitted, the questionnaires are stored on CIRAD Kobotoolbox platform that is located on a
627 server located in the European Union. Data are then downloaded and stored securely on encrypted
628 electronic devices. At the end of the study, data will be archived in a secure manner to a limited duration
629 of 30 years. To comply with the FAIR rules, non-sensitive or secret data will be made publicly available
630 on the dataverse of CIRAD, and only fully anonymized or aggregated will be made available so that
631 individuals' re-identification will not be possible.

632 **Data Analysis overview**

633 Quantitative data analysis is being conducted to test the main hypotheses of the project, building on the
634 different theoretical and methodological frameworks described in the conceptual framework. We
635 present here a general description of the methods envisioned, but the detailed description of methods
636 effectively implemented to treat the different research questions will be provided in the different articles
637 related to each question. An overview of the research questions, hypothesis and analysis conducted is
638 provided in S2 (Study Design table).

639 First, a set of analysis is being conducted to establish a typology of farmers' seed and information
640 sourcing networks, and assess the socio-economic factors associated to these different groups of
641 practices. In this objective, we combine clustering and indicator-based approaches to gain a better

642 assessment, following the classical personal network analysis methods (Wasserman and Faust 1994,
643 McCarty et al. 2019). Multivariate analysis (PCA) and classification algorithms such as HAC
644 (hierarchical ascendant classification) are being respectively applied to the matrices of farms' seed or
645 information sources. Network metrics are being computed at the farm level to measure the following
646 indicators of personal (ego) networks: (i) the number of direct seed or information sourcing ties a farm
647 has (indegree, Freeman 1979), (ii) the diversity of ties derived from Shannon entropy that has the
648 advantage of being robust to missing data and almost insensitive to network size (Blüthgen 2006), (iii)
649 the geographical extent of networks, based on the maximum geographical distance of ties. Generalized
650 Linear Models are being used to test for the correlations either between farm's membership to the
651 different seed or information network groups or between farms' network measures on one hand, and on
652 the other hand, farms' socioeconomic variables such as the gender, age, and ethnicity of the house heads
653 or the economic status of the household.

654 Second, a specific set of analysis is being conducted to assess gender differences in their reports of seed
655 baskets and sourcing. This analysis is only be conducted on data collected in Senegal and Madagascar
656 as interviews could not be conducted with women in Morocco. First, analysis is being conducted to
657 compare the reports of men farm heads VS women concerning the whole farm seed basket and sourcing.
658 This comparison between the population of married men and women interviewed concerning the farm
659 seed baskets will allow to assess whether some gender bias exists, by testing if men and women differ
660 in the frequency of reported crop cultivated, seed lots self-production, and type and characteristics of
661 seed sources. Second, we test whether women's seed baskets and sources are accurately reported by
662 men when they are interviewed about this aspect at the farm level. In this objective, we compare the
663 answers of men and women involved in seed sourcing within the same household to assess the match
664 of their reports concerning the crop cultivated by women. This is be conducted only for Senegal data,
665 where a specific survey is done with women in a subsample of households.

666 Third, the relationship between farms' seed and information sourcing networks on the one hand, and
667 the crop diversity level in farms and the crop turnover over time on the other hand, is being tested.
668 Measures of the level of crop diversity on each farm and in each year are computed based on the number
669 of species and varieties. Then, the turnover of crop species and varieties over time is computed using
670 Bray-Curtis dissimilarity to compare crop composition at the farm level between pairs of consecutive
671 years (Magurran and Henderson 2010). These measures will be computed separately at the species level
672 and at the varietal level for each species. Each measure is aggregated over time into a summary multi-
673 annual index, computed as the ratio of their mean over the five years of the study to their standard
674 deviation (Renard and Tilman 2019). We build on recently developed multilevel linear modeling
675 approaches to test the respective effect of community versus farm network structure on crop diversity
676 and turnover measures (Agneessens and Koskinen 2016). Farm network measures is computed as
677 described above, and four community network measures are computed: (i) global network diversity

678 based on both the abundance of each actor category and the probabilities of interaction between these
679 categories (Ohlman et al. 2019). Actors categories are defined depending on their nature - individual,
680 governmental, non-governmental or private organizations - their geographical location and their
681 socioeconomic attribute, (ii) the density of the ties in the network (Wasserman and Faust 1994).
682 Depending on our capacity to estimate global measures of network structure, synthetic measures
683 reflecting how close a network is to a core-periphery structure may be computed based on the outputs
684 of Stochastic Block Models (Gonzalez et al. 2020). To deal with the network's interdependence issue,
685 fixed and random community-level effects are included, as well as an autocorrelation component
686 (Snijders and Boskers 2012). Characteristics of farms (e.g. livelihood activities), communities (e.g.
687 size), and sites (e.g. weather data), are included as covariates in the model to control for their effect.

688 Last, tests are being conducted to assess to what extent the characteristics of farms' seed and
689 information sourcing networks relate to proxies of resilience outcomes at the farm level, namely more
690 stable agricultural production over time, and an enhanced capacity to cover their food and financial
691 needs. Based on the analysis presented above, we expect to identify group of farms presenting particular
692 network characteristics related to a higher level of crop diversity and crop turnover. We test if the farms
693 presenting these connectivity characteristics have a more stable agricultural production over time and
694 better cover their needs over several years as compared to other farms. An index of crop production is
695 being computed at the farm level for each year as the aggregation of the quantities harvested for each
696 crop species converted in energy (calories). It is then be aggregated over time into a summary multi-
697 annual index, computed as for crop diversity. We test if the mean production differs between farms
698 groups using variance analysis, and if needs coverage differs using adapted rank tests.

699 **Challenges and perspectives**

700 Through the protocol described, we expect to improve the general understanding of the role of seed and
701 information sourcing practices in smallholder farmers' access to crop diversity, and to what extent this
702 contributes to their resilience to perturbations. Collecting comparable data within a common framework
703 and field setting over different study sites is a key challenge to progress in the general understanding of
704 the processes studied. As detailed in the introduction, several case-studies investigated the relationship
705 between crop diversity and seed sourcing practices, leading to diverging conclusions. The differences
706 in methods and contexts of these studies strongly limited our capacity to identify the origin of these
707 differences and their implications. Conducting large scale longitudinal surveys is hence needed to
708 complement case studies and bring general conclusions, but it raises particular challenges which we
709 believe it is important to share with our research community. Large panel and longitudinal surveys on
710 smallholder seed and information networks, covering thousands of respondents and repeated for several
711 years, are not common in smallholder seed systems research. ARISER protocol is the first of this kind,

712 covering four consecutive years and 2000 households in three different although comparable study sites.
713 The quantitative approach based on this protocol presents some strengths, but also some weaknesses,
714 as discussed above. We thus believe that sharing this protocol and the challenges we met along its
715 design, test and implementation can be of interest for the design of future research in this domain and
716 worth to be shared with our research community. These aspects should also be considered when
717 examining the results and conclusions that can be drawn from the application of the protocol.

718 Conducting large surveys on seed systems requires to compromise on the level of details and accuracy
719 of data. Generally speaking, large surveys makes it much more difficult to overcome the local norms
720 and taboos as compared to case studies that allow to build proximity and trust with survey participants
721 and makes possible to extend interview duration and details and access to information on sensitive
722 aspects. This especially affected our ability to recruit women, as explained in the methods section. It
723 also limited our capacity to get details about the identity of seed or information provider, affecting in
724 turn the ability to conduct complete networks data sampling as initially planned.

725 Combining this quantitative survey data with fine-grain qualitative and comprehensive surveys is thus
726 crucial to gain a good understanding of the processes at stake. The presented protocol put the focus on
727 quantitative methods, but we insist on the importance of combining it with qualitative data, as well as
728 extensive literature review. This is especially needed to get a complete understanding of the governance
729 of seed systems and market dynamics that play a key role in smallholder farmers' access to seed. It
730 allows also to get into the local rules and norms that drive seed and information circulation in rural
731 societies, and document more diffuse or hidden processes that could not be documented through
732 questionnaires. In ARISER project, case studies are conducted by students in each study sites, which
733 provides an in-depth understanding of the local crop diversity management practices. A serious game
734 was designed to obtain complementary data about farmers' decision-making regarding seed and
735 information sourcing. We are conducting a literature review covering scientific publications and reports
736 as well as official documents concerning public policies and legal frameworks related to the seed sector.
737 Last, workshops are organized with farmers and local development organizations for discussing our
738 results, which is decisive for building robust and accurate conclusions.

739 The presented protocol is expected to make significant contributions to research on smallholder seed
740 systems by offering a unified framework for conducting future comparable research. Such a framework
741 will allow to implement a large-scale assessment of the effect of different crop seed and information
742 sourcing modalities on smallholders' access to crop diversity across different contexts. This will address
743 an important challenge in this research field, as scholars claim that local social networks involved in
744 crop seed and information diffusion play a key role in smallholders' access to crop diversity (Coomes
745 et al. 2015, Pautasso et al. 2013), but concrete evidence for which characteristics of these networks is
746 lacking. This protocol is also expected to advance our understanding of the processes involved in
747 smallholder resilience in a context of high climate variability. This is particularly important as research

748 on climate adaptation has paid limited attention to crop diversity management compared with other
749 adaptation measures, despite its importance for rural communities (Schlingmann et al. 2021). Crop
750 diversity access is frequently mentioned as a pillar of smallholders' resilience, despite the lack of robust
751 scientific evidences and understanding of the processes driving this access (Bravo-Peña and Yoder
752 2024). This protocol will contribute in feeding this research front by assessing whether crop seed and
753 associated information sourcing modalities play a role in the capacity of smallholder farmers to meet
754 their needs and get more stable crop production over time. Last, this protocol will contribute to improve
755 the general understanding of inequalities in access to crop diversity between the different categories of
756 farmers in rural communities, which has never been assessed systematically across different contexts
757 to date, to our knowledge.

758 By advancing knowledge on these aspects, this protocol is expected to contribute to concrete impacts
759 beyond research, for agricultural development and policies. Improving and adapting the governance
760 mechanisms and institutions related to seed systems is essential for addressing the specific needs of
761 smallholder (Westengen, Dalle and Mulesa 2023; Louwaars and Manicad 2022). This protocol will
762 contribute to this by bringing the full range of smallholder crop diversity management systems into
763 decision-making arenas dedicated to agricultural development, in which the "multiple-evidence based
764 approach" remains marginal (Tengö et al. 2014). This approach is gaining recognition in other policy
765 arenas, including IPBES for biodiversity (Tengö et al. 2017) and IPCC for climate change (Ford et al.
766 2016) as its ability to tackle major societal challenges is widely acknowledged. Through this protocol
767 and its application in different contexts, ARISER research supports the development of this approach
768 in agricultural decision-making. We expect that this protocol will allow decision-makers and
769 development agencies to get a better understanding of which characteristics of smallholder seed systems
770 makes them more resilient to shocks, and which categories of farmers are more vulnerable from this
771 perspective. The understanding of seed and information circulation processes this protocol will provide
772 is a key for co-designing inclusive and equitable mechanisms to enhance farmers' access to crop
773 diversity.

774 **Conclusion**

775 We hope that sharing this research protocol will pave the way for further studies in a variety of contexts,
776 helping to progress on the general understanding of how seed and related information networks affect
777 farmers' ability to use crop diversity in the face of disturbances, and the impact of social inequalities on
778 this. Such understanding is instrumental for seed systems decision-making, in the current context where
779 the broad diversity of seed sourcing modalities implemented by farmers is not considered and where
780 most actions target the centralization of this sector. We hope that this protocol, which is the first
781 designed to collect comparable data across different contexts and over several years, will contribute to

782 build actionable knowledge in the perspective to enhance smallholder's involvement in the codesign of
783 more adapted seed systems policies and legal frameworks.

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793 improve some English sentences in this article, as authors are not native English speakers.

794 **Supporting information**

795 S1: Detailed questionnaire for farm surveys, illustration on Senegal site. NB: column A gives the section
796 number or the type of answer (text, integer, decimal, unique choice, multiple choice, yes/no); column
797 B indicates if the question is asked each year or not; column C gives the section title or the question
798 asked; Column D gives details of the proposed answers or the types of answers.

799 S2: Study design table, summarizing the research question, hypothesis and analyses conducted.

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971

Section number or type of answer	Questions asked each year	Title or question asked	Choice of answers
A.		A. INTRODUCTION	
A.1		A.1 PRESENTATION OF THE ARISER STUDY	
	Yes	Summary, Process, and Purposes of the Surveys : The ARISER study aims to better understand how different crops enable farmers in [commune name] to cope with disruptions, particularly climatic ones. This study also seeks to understand where farmers obtain their seeds for these various crops and how these different seed supply strategies influence households' ability to cope with disruptions. The results from this survey will lead to scientific publications, presentations at conferences, or informational documents for development stakeholders. We will try to disseminate the results and discuss them with all the villages in the area so that all residents of the commune can benefit. All written reports from this study will be delivered to the village chief and will be accessible to anyone who wishes to see them. If you wish to obtain information about the follow-up of the project, you can contact the lead researcher at any time.	
	Yes	Participants' Rights : You are voluntarily participating in this survey, which means that you are free to participate or not, and you can choose not to answer one or more questions asked of you. Your participation is free of charge, with no financial compensation or cost to you. You can stop the survey and withdraw from this study at any time, without needing to justify yourself. To do so, simply contact the lead researcher. The individuals responsible for this survey ensure that your participation or withdrawal has no negative consequences for you. Thus, your responses and identifying data will only be known to the survey team. The data from this survey will only be accessible to those in charge of the survey and the researchers associated with the project for analysis purposes, and they will be secured through password-protected access. The results that will be disseminated at the end of this project will not allow you to be identified, as only aggregated data, that is, global data, will be shared. If any changes to the project's objectives or the use of your responses are considered, we will inform you of these changes and request your consent again. You have the option to indicate now whether you would agree to have your data potentially reused for other research projects (other than the current project). Your refusal will not have any negative consequences for you and does not call into question your participation in this survey. If you agree, we will ask for your consent again for this reuse.	
	Yes	Data Protection : The information collected by Cirad as the data controller is gathered for the purpose of studying the role of seed supply methods in the resilience and food security of farming households, for research purposes. This processing is based on your explicit consent, expressed verbally and signed by the witness before the interviews begin. Your data will be kept for the duration of the study (5 years, from 2022 to 2027) and up to 30 years after the end of the study. This extended retention is initially necessary to allow the exploitation of the data for publications for 10 years after the end of the study, then for an additional 15 years to allow, if necessary, comparative analyses by other projects. At the end of this retention period, the data will be destroyed. The information collected is intended for the ARISER research team and subcontractors involved in the study and may be communicated to partners under confidentiality conditions and within the sole framework of ARISER. In accordance with the applicable regulations, concerning the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), you have the rights of access, rectification, erasure, and portability (when applicable) concerning your data, as well as the right to restrict and object to their processing for legitimate reasons. You can exercise these rights by contacting the Data Protection Officer of the data controller at dpo@cirad.fr. You also have the right to lodge a complaint at any time with the competent authority (in France, the CNIL).	
	Yes	Protection of Traditional Knowledge and Know-How Associated with Genetic Resources : In the context of access and benefit-sharing (ABS), traditional knowledge and know-how associated with genetic resources refer to the knowledge, innovations, and practices of indigenous and local communities related to genetic resources. They result from the experience gained by people over centuries, are adapted to local needs, cultures, and environments, and are passed down through generations. The collection of this traditional knowledge and know-how requires compliance with the procedures set by the Nagoya Protocol of 2010, particularly the fair and equitable sharing of benefits arising from research. In the context of this survey, you are sharing with us information about traditional knowledge and know-how associated with local genetic resources. The project has taken the necessary steps to comply with the Nagoya Protocol.	
A.2		A.2 CONSENT REQUEST	

		<p>1. Have you received and understood the information that was communicated to you?</p> <p>2. Have you been able to ask questions?</p> <p>3. Do you understand that you can decide to stop participating in the survey at any time?</p> <p>4. Do you agree to participate in the study?</p> <p>5. Do you understand your rights regarding your personal data?</p> <p>6. Do you agree that the data collected in this study can be used according to the purposes, retention period, and recipients indicated in the information letter?</p> <p>7. Do you agree that your data can be reused for another project? (if applicable)</p> <p>8. Do you agree to be contacted again for another survey? (if applicable)</p>	
Yes/no	Yes	Does the respondent give their consent verbally?	
Unique choice	Yes	Name of the interviewer	List of the local interviewers recruited
B. SURVEY IDENTIFICATION			
date	Yes	Survey date	
Unique choice	Yes	Name of the surveyed village	List of the villages selected for the study
Unique choice	Yes	Name of the surveyed hamlet or neighborhood	List of hamlets or neighborhoods studied in the village when applicable
geopoint	No	GPS coordinates of the house	GPS coordinates given by Kobo application, or by GPS Garmin
Unique choice	Yes	Farm identifier (ID)	List of the farms selected for the study and identified by a unique number
C. FARM			
C.1 FIELD			
C.1.a Land status and field surface area			
Integer or decimal	No	What is the total area of agricultural land that your household owns?	
Yes/no	No	Does your household have a home garden?	
Multiple-choice	No	What are the main crops you grow each year in your home garden?	List of the most commonly crops species and categories of crops species encountered in the study area (e.g. Waterme
	Yes	Over the last agricultural season :	
Integer or decimal		How many fields in total have you cultivated ? (the total number of fields includes owned fields, rented fields, borrowed fields, and sharecropped fields)	
Integer or decimal		If you left some land uncultivated, what total area it represents? (e.g. land left fallow)	Different units of area measurement are provided (e.g. km ² , hectares, m ²)
C.1.b Description of each field cultivated over the last agricultural season			
	No	Questions asked for each field cultivated over the last agricultural season :	
Multiple-choice		What is the type of land tenure ?	List of the different cases and possibilities encountered in the study area
Integer or decimal		What is the area of the field ?	Different units of area measurement are provided (e.g. km ² , hectares, m ²)
Multiple-choice		What are the different types of soil present in the field ?	List of the different cases and possibilities encountered in the study area
Multiple-choice		What are the different species of cereals, legumes, and tubers that you cultivated in this field during the previous agricultural season?	Exhaustive list of crop species of cereals, legumes and tubers inventoried in the study area (e.g. maize, sorgi
Yes/no		Did you allow the livestock to graze on the residues from the previous crops ?	
Multiple-choice		What are the different species of cereals, legumes, and tubers that you sown in this field over the last agricultural season ?	Exhaustive list of crop species of cereals, legumes and tubers inventoried in the study area (e.g. maize, sorgi
Multiple-choice		What are the crop species, other than cereals, legumes, and tubers, that you sown in this field over the last agricultural season ?	Exhaustive list of the other crop species inventoried in the study area (e.g. secondary crops, bissap, okra)
	No	If several crop species have been sown in this field over the last agricultural season :	
Unique choice		How are these crops species associated in the field ?	List of the different crop species associations observed in the fields in the study area (e.g. intercropping, mixed, in sep

C.1.c			C.1.c Farming practices		
	Yes	Questions asked for all the field cultivated over the last agricultural season :			
Multiple-choice		What type of tillage have you performed on your fields ?			<i>List of the different cases and possibilities encountered in the study area (e.g. manual, mecanized)</i>
Yes/no		Did you use chemical fertilizers ?			
Multiple-choice		Did you use manure ? And how ?			<i>List of the different cases and possibilities encountered in the study area (e.g. application in all fields, applic</i>
Multiple-choice		Did you use products to eliminate insects, diseases, or fungi ?			<i>List of the different cases and possibilities encountered in the study area (e.g. chemical product, biologic pro</i>
	No	If there are perennial species in your fields over the last agricultural season :			
Multiple-choice		What are the perennial species ?			<i>List of perennial species observed in the fields in the study area (e.g. mango tree, neem tree, jujube tree)</i>
Integer or decimal		How many do you have approximately ?			
Integer or decimal		On how many fields are they present? (if present on all fields, please indicate the total number of cultivated fields)			
C.2			C.2 CROP SPECIES		
	Yes	List of crop species cultivated over the last agricultural season			
Multiple-choice		List of all the species of cereals, legumes, and tubers that you cultivated across all your fields : (Do not include homegarden crops and do not forget secondary crops occupying small areas in the fields)			<i>Exhaustive list of crop species of cereals, legumes and tubers inventoried in the study area (e.g. maize, sorgo</i>
Yes/no		Do you confirm that you have not cultivated the crops that were not checked in the previous list? (the interviewer should list all unchecked crops before answering and ensure that no crop species were forgotten or added)			
	Yes	Question asked for each species of cereal, legume, and tuber checked in the previous list:			
Integer or decimal		How many varieties of this specie did you sown across all your fields over the last agricultural season ?			
C.2.a/b/c			C.2.a/b/c CROP VARIETY		
	Yes	Sections C.2.a/b/c : questions asked for each variety counted for each species of cereal, legume, and tuber checked in the previous list			
C.2.a			C.2.a Named variety, sowing and harvesting		
	Yes	Over the last agricultural season :			
Unique choice		What is the name of the variety you sown ?			<i>Exhaustive list of the 28 named varieties of cereals, legumes and tubers inventoried in the study area</i>
Unique choice		What is the nature of the variety you sown ?			<i>List of the different cases and possibilities encountered in the study area (e.g. local farmer variety, introduced variety</i>
Unique choice		Would you spontaneously use one of these terms to describe this variety ? (list adapted to each study site, illustration in Senegal study site)			<i>possible choices : local (thiossane, cossaan) introduite (récemment introduite) certifiée, ne sait pas</i>
Yes/no		Did your parents already cultivated this variety ?			
Yes/no		Is it the first time you grow this variety ?			
Yes/no		Did you cultivated it last year ?			
Unique choice		Even if you don't grow it each year, since approximately how long are growing it ?			<i>possible choices : ...<5 years; 5<...<10; 10<...<20; 20<...<40; 40<...</i>
Integer or decimal		What quantity did you sown ?			<i>Different units of weight measurement are provided (e.g. kilogram, tonne, gram, 50 kg sack)</i>
Unique choice		When did you sown : beginning, middle or end of which month of the year ?			
Yes/no		Did you do a re-sow ?			
Integer or decimal		What quantity did you harvested ? (enter 0 if there was no harvest)			<i>Different units of weight measurement are provided (e.g. kilogram, tonne, gram, 50 kg sack)</i>
Unique choice		Do you count your harvest in grains, shells, ears, or pods ?			
Unique choice		When did you harvested : beginning, middle or end of which month of the year ?			
Multiple-choice		If no harvest : how do you explain that ?			<i>List of 22 main reasons described by the farmers of the study areas (e.g. soil fertility issues, excessive rainfall, no germ</i>
	Yes	If harvested :			

Unique choice		Are you satisfied with the harvest ?	
Multiple-choice		If the harvest was poor or unsatisfactory : in your opinion, what are the reasons for this?	List of 22 main reasons described by the farmers of the study areas (e.g. soil fertility issues, excessive rainfall, no germ
Multiple-choice		If the harvest was satisfactory or very satisfactory : In your opinion, what are the reasons for this?	List of 8 main reasons described by the farmers of the study areas (e.g. favorable weather conditions, good-quality se
Unique choice		Using the terms "not at all, a little, a lot, all," estimate the share of the total harvest that was intended for: -sale -human consumption -animal feed -to be used as seeds for the following year	
Multiple-choice		Why do you prefer this variety over another ? Or what are the advantages of cultivating this variety ?	List of 23 main reasons described by the farmers of the study area (e.g. High grain yield, high selling price, resistant to
C.2.b			
C.2.b		C.2.b Information sources	
Unique choice	Yes	Where did your knowledge about the variety come from that made you decide to cultivate it ? (select the main source of information)	-From personal experience -From observing a neighbor's field -Through family tradition/generational knowledge transfer -From common practices among farmers in the village, commune, or region -From advice given by a farmer -From advice given by a seller (market, local shop, specialized store) -From advice given by an agricultural project (government, NGO, cooperative, association) -From information shared via media (radio, newspaper, television) -From information shared on social media -Can't remember
text	Yes	If the information came from a project, cooperative, or farmers' organization, what is its name?	
	Yes	Where was this source of information located ? (i.e., place of observation, location of the market, store, farmer who provided the advice, or project)	(Official lists available on the government website)
Unique choice		Name of the region in the study country	List of the regions of Senegal
Unique choice		Name of the departement in the study region	List of the departments in the study region (Kaffrine)
Unique choice		Name of the village in the study department	List of the villages/cities in the study departmment (Kaffrine)
Whatever the answer given for the type of information source:			
Unique choice		What is the nature of your relationship with the person who gave you the advice, or with whom you made the observation ?	-I don't know them. -I don't know them personally, but I recognize who they are (it's an acquaintance). -It's a friend. -It's a family member -field neighbor -village neighbor -both -neither
Unique choice		If the source of information was located in the study department: is the person a neighboring farmer ? someone from the village ?	
	Yes	If the person associated with the source of information is someone known, a friend, or a family member :	
Unique choice		Gender	
text		Last name	
text		First name	
Unique choice		Age category	List of 6 age categories (<20 years, 20-30, 30-40 year, 40-50, 50-60, and >60 years)
	Yes	If the person is a family member :	
Unique choice		Does the person belong to your own family or to your spouse's family ?	
Unique choice		What is the nature of the kinship tie ?	List of kinship ties across three generations according to the gender of the respondent (e.g mother, father, brother, si
C.2.c			
C.2.c		C.2.c Seed sources	
	Yes	Over the last agricultural season :	
Integer or decimal		How many different sources (or seed lots) do the seeds of the variety you cultivated come from ? (seed lot : all the seed of the same variety obtained from the same source on the same date by the household)	
	Yes	Questions asked for each seed lot counted :	

Unique choice	Was this seed lot self-produced (seeds kept from a previous harvest), or sourced outside the farm last year ?	-Self produced -Sourced out of the farm
Yes If the seeds were self-produced on the farm:		
Unique choice	How did you select your seeds?	-Selection in the field -Selection at the granary/storage (stored harvest bags) -Other
Unique choice	Where did you store your seeds before using them for the last agricultural season ?	-Traditional granary (sakk) -Keurgui storage -Deukébi storage -Household storage -In a tree -Other
Unique choice	When was the last time you obtained these seeds? (i.e. last acquisition before self-production)	-Can't remember -Between 2 and 5 years ago -Between 5 and 10 years ago -More than 10 years ago -Inherited
Yes If the seeds have been inherited (answer "inherited" above I.108) :		
Unique choice	Does the person belong to your own family or to your spouse's family ?	
Unique choice	What is the nature of the kinship tie ?	List of kinship ties across three generations according to the gender of the respondent (e.g mother, father, brother, si
text	Last name	
text	First name	
Unique choice	Gender	
Unique choice	Age category	List of 6 age categories (< 20 years, 20-30, 30-40 year, 40-50, 50-60, and > 60 years)
Yes If the seeds were not self-produced on the farm (answer "out of the farm" I.104) :		
Multiple-choice	Why did you restock your seeds ?	List of 8 main reasons described by the farmers of the study area (e.g. lost of the variety, test of a new variety, opportu -Louma (weekly market) -Daily market in the village -Specialized store (seed and agricultural supplies) -Village shop -Farmer -Farmers' organization (association, cooperative) -Agricultural project (government, NGO) -Seed multiplier (certified seed producer) -Can't remember
Unique choice	Where do the seeds of the variety you cultivated over the last agricultural season come from ?	
Unique choice	How were these seeds obtained: purchase, donation, barter, or in exchange for other seeds?	
Unique choice	If the seed source is a market, what type of seller was it ?	-local farmers selling punctually the own harvest -local seed resellers (buying and reselling seeds in their community) -external seed sellers -other
text	If the seed source is a specialized store, village shop, project (government, NGO), cooperative, or farmers' association: what is its name ?	
Yes Whatever the answer given for the type of seed source: where was it located ? (Official lists available on the government website)		
Unique choice	Name of the region in study country	List of the regions of Senegal
Unique choice	Name of the departement in study region	List of the departments in the study region (Kaffrine)
Unique choice	Name of the village in study department	List of the villages/cities in the study departement (Kaffrine)
Yes Whatever the answer given for the type of seed source:		
Unique choice	What is your relationship with the person from whom you obtained the seeds ?	-I don't know them. -I don't know them personally, but I recognize who they are (it's an acquaintance). -It's a friend. -It's a family member

Unique choice		If the seed source was located in the study department: is the person a neighboring farmer ? someone from the village ?	-field neighbor -village neighbor -both neither
	Yes	If the person associated with the seed source is someone known, a friend, or a family member :	
Unique choice		Gender	
text		Last name	
text		First name	
Unique choice		Age category	List of 6 age categories (<20 years, 20-30, 30-40 year, 40-50, 50-60, and >60 years)
	Yes	If the person is a family member :	
Unique choice		Does the person belongs to your own family or to your spouse's family ?	
Unique choice		What is the nature of the kinship tie ?	List of kinship ties across three generations according to the gender of the respondent (e.g mother, father, brother, si
	Yes	Except in cases where the seeds were given as a donation or inherited	
Multiple-choice		Why did you choose this source of seeds? (If the response relates to trust, inquire further about the basis of that trust before recording the answer)	List of 14 main reasons described by the farmers of the study area (e.g. unique source that provides those seeds, recon
D.		D. HOUSEHOLD	
D.1		D.1 HOUSEHOLD MEMBERS	
D.1.a	No	D.1.a Household head characteristics	
text		First name	
text		Last name	
Integer or decimal		Phone number	
Integer or decimal		Age	
Unique choice		Gender	
Unique choice		Native language group (list of groups adapted to each study site, illustration in Senegal study site)	Exhaustive list of the different ethnic groups identified in the study area (e.g. Sereer, Peulh)
Unique choice		Region, department and village of birth	Official lists available on the government website
Unique choice		Education level	
Integer or decimal		How many years have you been farming as the head of the agricultural operation?	
Multiple-choice		Do you have a pecific social status within the village ? (or several, adapted to each study site, illustration in Senegal study site)	List of the different cases encountered in the study area (e.g. village chief, neighborhood chief, lineage chief, notable,
Yes/no		Are you a beneficiary of one or more agricultural projects? (e.g.NGO project, government project)	
Multiple-choice		Name of the projects	List of agricultural projects identified in the study area
Yes/no		Are you a member of one or more farmers' organizations? (e.g.cooperative, association)	
Multiple-choice		Name of the farmers' organization	List of farmers' organizations identified in the study area
D.1.b	No	D.1.b Household composition	
Integer or decimal		How many women are you married with and live in the household ?	
Integer or decimal		How many people, live in your household throughout the year or for a significant part of the year? (Other family members or not, welcomed by the head of the household, present at all meals or very regularly)	
		For each spouse counted :	
Unique choice		Native language group	Exhaustive list of the diffrent ethnic groups identified in the study area (e.g. Sereer, Peulh)
Unique choice		Region, department and village of birth	Official lists available on the government website
Integer or decimal		Age	

D.2			D.2 SOCIOECONOMIC DATA
D.2.a			D.2.a Household income-generating activities
No			
Multiple-choice	What are the different activities of the men and sons in your household that contribute solely to the household income ?		<i>List of the different activities described by the farmers in the study area (e.g. tailor, mechanic, carpenter, market gar</i>
Multiple-choice	What are the different activities of the women and daughters in your household that contribute solely to the household income ?		<i>List of the different activities described by the farmers in the study area (e.g. tailor, mechanic, carpenter, market gar</i>
Integer or decimal	Can you rank the different activities mentioned in descending order of importance in terms of income generated? (Use the same number if multiple activities have the same importance)		
D.2.b			D.2.b Household resources
No			
Multiple-choice	Does your household have these assets ? (list of assets adapted to each study site, illustration in Senegal study site)		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -House made of mud or bricks -Metal or durable fence -Solar panel -Television -Jakarta scooter -Well -Access to electricity via the collective grid -None
Yes/no	Has your household ever taken out a loan or borrowed money?		
Yes/no	Are there people who don't live in the house, but who receive money and/or produce from your farm ?		
Yes/no	Are there people who don't live in the house but send you money and/or food?		
D.2.c			D.2.c Domestic and livestock animals (adapted to each study site)
No			
Integer or decimal	How many draf animals does your household own ? (e.g. donkeys, horses, oxen - adapted to the study sites)		
Integer or decimal	Approximately, what is the size of your sheep flock (in number of heads) ?		
Integer or decimal	Approximately, what is the size of your cattle herd (in number of heads) ?		
D.2.d			D.2.d Labour force
Yes			
Over the last agricultural season :			
Yes/no	Did you use hired workforce to cultivate the fields ?		
Integer or decimal	If yes : what is the total amount of money you estimate for this expense related to hired workforce (in national currency) ?		
Integer or decimal	Including the people in your household and those living in the family compound, how many people in total (including yourself) helped with the work in the farm ?		
D.3			D.3 PERCEPTIONS OF LIFE CONDITIONS AND FOOD SECURITY
Yes			
Over the last agricultural season :			
Yes/no	Did you have any difficulties accessing the seeds you wanted to cultivate ?		
Multiple-choice	If yes : for which crop species ?		<i>Exhaustive list of crop species of cereals, legumes and tubers inventoried in the study area (e.g. maize, sorghum, mill</i>
Yes/no	Have you heard about other varieties that might interest you ?		
Yes/no	If yes: would it be easy for you to obtain information about these other varieties ?		
Unique choice	In light of the difficulties that family farming face in your area, do you think it is better to meet your needs satisfactorily by:		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Does not express an opinion -Cultivate multiple species -Focus on a reduced number of species

Unique choice	In your opinion, the income of your household and your productions:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Did not meet the family's needs (food, health/illness...) -Only barely met the family's needs (food, health/illness...) -Met the family's needs (food, health/illness...) -Very well met the family's needs (food, health/illness...)
Yes/no	Have you been forced to change your eating habits due to financial difficulties?	
Unique choice	If yes: how do you assess the significance of these changes?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Low -Medium -High
Yes/no	Have you had difficulties managing certain agricultural expenses ?	
Multiple-choice	If yes: what are these agricultural expenses?	<i>List of the different expenses described by the farmers of the study area (e.g. paying for labor, tractor, inputs)</i>
Unique choice	If yes: how do you assess the significance of these difficulties ?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Low -Medium -High
Yes/no	Have you had difficulties managing other expenses related to the family's living conditions? (e.g. school fees, health expenses, expenses for a ceremony)	
Unique choice	If yes: how do you assess the significance of these difficulties ?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Low -Medium -High

Question	Hypothesis	Sampling plan	Analysis Plan	Rationale for deciding the sensitivity of the test for confirming or disconfirming the hypothesis	Interpretation given different outcomes	Theory that could be shown wrong by the outcomes
(1) Do farms differ in their seed and information sourcing networks ?	Farms differ in the number of connections (incoming seed/information flows) and in the diversity of stakeholders they are connected to, as well as in the geographical extent of the connections.	Exhaustive sampling of farms in 8 to 12 communities in three study countries. Name generator protocol for documenting both seed/information circulation ties within the studied communities (complete sampling expected), and ties between farms and stakeholders out of the community.	Clustering based on the matrices of farms X seed or information sources. MCA + HCA.	For such qualitative multivariate data, the classical statistical method is an MCA followed by an HCA. Unfortunately the sensitivity of this method is not quantifiable.	If different clusters identified: Farms have different seed/information sourcing networks. This is expected to relate to differences in the diversity level and turnover of farm's crop baskets.	
(2) Are differences in farms' seed/information networks linked to their socioeconomic characteristics ?	Less wealthy households, and household whose heads are: members of ethnic minorities or migrants, women, or young people, present networks with fewer connections and less diverse personal seed/information networks. They are more frequently at the periphery of community networks	-	GLM to test to what extent : Farms' membership to the different clusters obtained in (1) and farms' personal network indicators, such as the number and diversity of connections, relate to socioeconomic indicators of farms and individual. If possible with the data (complete	T-tests from generalized linear models (GLM) are the book of the shelf approach for testing impacts of covariates on the response. As we don't have any prior knowledge on the effect size, we cannot run power analysis methods to assess the sampling size before hand.	If significant relationship between network indicators or clusters and socioeconomic indicators are observed, this would indicate that the different socioeconomic groups have different opportunities and constraints for sourcing seed and information.	

			network data available), Latent Block Models could be used to test for the effect of farms' characteristics on their connectivity profile within the global network.		This may impact their access to crop diversity.	
(3) To what extent are the crop diversity level and the crop turnover in farms over time related to their personal seed and information network characteristics, and to that of the community network ?	The crop diversity level and the crop turnover in farms over time are the highest (cf Fig.1): (i) in communities where seed and information networks present: intermediate connectivity levels, higher levels of diversity, and intermediate levels of core-periphery, or cluster structure. (ii) in farms presenting networks with more direct connections, higher diversity, less tie redundancy, and that occupy a more central position in the whole network.	-	Multilevel model inspired from Agneessens and Koskinen 2016 with individual and collective networks effects as explicative variables, and crop diversity and turnover indicators as outcome variables. Control variables will cover farm assets and agronomic characteristics. Depending on the availability of complete network data at the community level, the variables for community and individual networks structure will be adapted.		If an association is found between crop diversity level and turnover on the one hand, and personal / community network measures on the other hand, this would indicate that both are related. This can either mean that networks are significant drivers of crop diversity on-farm, or that crop diversity management in farms drives their seed or information sourcing networks.	If this relationship is not verified, this would mean that previous claims concerning the linkages between farm's crop diversity and seed /information networks would not be verified (Labeyrie et al. 2021)
(4) Do farms' presenting network characteristics associated to higher crop diversity /	Farms where seed and information networks include the collective and farm network patterns		Multilevel model inspired from Agneessens and Koskinen 2016 with individual and		If an association is found between declared crop production stability and needs fulfilment	

<p>turnover are related to a higher and more stable declared crop production over time and households' needs fulfilment?</p>	<p>listed in (3) will have higher and more stable crop production over time, and will declare a more stable and high level of needs fulfilment.</p>		<p>collective networks effects (explicative variables) and pluriannual indicators of reported multicrop production stability and level, and households' need fulfilment.</p>		<p>on the one hand, and the personal / community network measures associated to (3) on the other hand, this would indicate that networks patterns associated to a higher crop diversity or turnover are related to a higher resilience of farms' to perturbations .</p> <p>In case a relationship is found with network characteristics others than those observed in (3), this may indicate that other features (e.g. seed quantity rather than diversity) are important for farm's resilience.</p>	
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Guidance Notes

- **Question:** articulate each research question being addressed in one sentence.
- **Hypothesis:** where applicable, a prediction arising from the research question, stated in terms of specific variables rather than concepts. Where the testability of one or more hypotheses depends on the verification of auxiliary assumptions (such as positive controls, tests of intervention fidelity, manipulation checks, or any other quality checks), any tests of such assumptions should be listed as hypotheses. Stage 1 proposals that do not seek to test hypotheses can ignore or delete this column.
- **Sampling plan:** For proposals using inferential statistics, the details of the statistical sampling plan for the specific hypothesis (e.g power analysis, Bayes Factor Design Analysis, ROPE etc). For proposals that do not use inferential statistics, include a description and justification of the sample size.
- **Analysis plan:** For hypothesis-driven studies, the specific test(s) that will confirm or disconfirm the hypothesis. For non-hypothesis-driven studies, the test(s) that will answer the research question.
- **Rationale for deciding the sensitivity of the test for confirming or disconfirming the hypothesis:** For hypothesis-driven studies that employ inferential statistics, an explanation of how the authors determined a relevant effect size for statistical power analysis, equivalence testing, Bayes factors, or other approach.
- **Interpretation given different outcomes:** A prospective interpretation of different potential outcomes, making clear which outcomes would confirm or disconfirm the hypothesis.

- **Theory that could be shown wrong by the outcomes:** Where the proposal is testing a theory, make clear what theory could be shown to be wrong, incomplete, or otherwise inadequate by the outcomes of the research.